

Incidental Findings of Microfilaria at Unusual Sites in Tertiary Care Hospital, Raigarh, Chhattisgarh**Bhagat Kiranlata¹, Naik Reena², Bansal Aarti³, Gajendra Megha⁴, Minj Manoj K⁵**¹Assistant Professor in Pathology, MBBS MD, (Pathology), Govt Medical College (LSLAMGMC) Raigarh, Chhattisgarh²Associate Professor in Pathology, MBBS, DNB (Pathology), Govt Medical College (LSLAMGMC) Raigarh, Chhattisgarh³Assistant Professor in Pathology, MBBS, MD (Pathology), Govt Medical College (LSLAMGMC) Raigarh, Chhattisgarh⁴Demonstrator in Pathology, MBBS, MD (Pathology), Govt Medical College (LSLAMGMC) Raigarh, Chhattisgarh⁵Professor and HOD, Dept of Pathology, Govt Medical College (LSLAMGMC) Raigarh, Chhattisgarh

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Bhagat Kiranlata

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Abstract:**Background:** Microfilaria, the tropical parasitic larvae of filarial nematodes parasite is the major public health problem in most of the state of India that are typically found in the bloodstream, skin and lymphatic system. However, our research reveals an unprecedented presence of microfilaria at unusual sites, challenging the conventional understanding of their habitat.**Aims:** This study was investigated and to document these incidental findings of microfilaria at unusual sites in a different pathological sample such as FNAC, fluid cytology and Histopathological examination, shedding light on the unexplored territories of microfilaria infestation.**Material and Methods:** This 4 year's Retrospective study was done from January 2019 to December 2022. All the cytological fluids, FNAC smears and histopathological slides were reviewed.**Result:** Total 16 cases were diagnosed as Microfilaria. Out of which 8 cases found in FNAC, 5 cases in Fluid cytology and 3 cases in Histopathological examinations. Among them different sites were breast, thyroid, scrotum, lymph node and nodular swelling in forearm including pleural and ascitic fluid.**Conclusion:** Swelling at any part of the body should be considered as differential diagnosis of microfilaria. So, FNAC, fluid cytological smears and histopathological examination should be done carefully. Our findings highlight the need for an expanded diagnostic approach and improved treatment strategies.**Keywords:** Microfilaria, FNAC, Fluid Cytology, Histopathological examination, unexpected locations.

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Introduction

Filarial nematodes offspring are responsible for debilitating diseases, with microfilaria being the infectious stage. Filariasis is a major parasitic disease in many tropical and subtropical countries. [1,2] It is endemic in India, especially in the states of Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, Kerala, and Gujarat.[1]

Lymphatic filariasis is increasing every year and over 553.7 million people are at risk of lymphatic filariasis in India. [1,3] Despite the high incidence in India, the occurrence of filarial nodules and their diagnosis by lymph node, breast lesions, thyroid goitre, scrotal swelling, subcutaneous swelling, pleural fluid and ascitic fluid is unusual.[5] While their presence in traditional sites is well-documented, recent discoveries have hinted at their

existence in unconventional locations. This study aims to investigate microfilaria infestation in diverse pathological samples.

Most of the previous literatures revealed an incidental diagnosis of microfilariae in cytology smears of different locations including breast, thyroid, soft tissue, lymph nodes, salivary glands, and effusion fluids.[2,4] In our study, we found microfilaria parasites incidentally in biopsy of lymph node and scrotum; in FNAC of the inguinal lymph nodes, thyroid, breast and in scrotal, ascitic and pleural fluid.

Material and Method

This study was started, after the permission of ethical committee. The 4-year retrospective study

was conducted in tertiary care hospital, in the Department of Pathology. The duration of the study was January 2019 to December 2022. Total number of pathological samples received in FNAC were 1382, biopsy samples were 2889 and fluid samples were 618, out of which total 16 pathological samples from various sites were found positive for filaria incidentally. Samples were examined using cytological, histopathological samples under microscope to detect microfilariae. All the cytological and histopathological smears were restain and reevaluated. FNAC was done by using 22–23-gauge needle attached with 10 cc syringe. Air-dried smears were stained with Leishman-Giemsa stain and alcohol-fixed smears were stained with Papanicolaou stain. For histopathological study H and E stain was done. The aspirated fluids were centrifuged and smears were prepared from centrifuged deposits. All the

cases were reviewed and relevant data were analysed.

Result

In our study we found 16 cases of microfilaria from different sites and in different samples like fluid cytology, FNAC and Biopsies. Out of 16 cases 9 were male and 7 were female. Age distribution of cases showed a wide range from 19 to 73 years of age. Most common age group involved were between 41 to 50 years about 6 cases followed by 51 to 60 years of age in which 4 cases were found. Out of 16 cases predominantly 8 cases were found in FNAC samples, out of which 3 cases were from breast lump which is congruent with the study of Ruchee et al [14], followed by 5 cases in fluid cytology that includes 3 pleural fluid and 1 case of each ascitic and scrotal fluid and 3 cases in biopsy.

Figure 1: Clinical picture of multinodular Goitre, positive for Microfilaria in FNAC

Figure 2: Fluid cytology of microfilaria in scrotal swelling (40Xview, Giemsa stain)

Figure 3: FNAC Thyroid showing an adult microfilaria with benign thyroid follicular cells, (40X, Giemsa stain)

Figure 4: Inguinal lymph node- microphotograph showing fragment of gravid microfilaria (40Xview, Giemsa stain)

Figure 5: FNAC-Breast showing clusters of benign epithelial cells along with microfilaria (40X, Geimsa stain)

Figure 6: FNAC Breast showing microfilaria with clusters of larvae (40Xview, Geimsa stain)

Figure 7: Biopsy inguinal lymph node showing microfilaria (zooming view of 40Xview, H&E Stain)

Figure 8: Biopsy breast tissue showing adult microfilaria embedded in stroma. (Zooming view 40X, H&E Stain)

Table 1: Distribution of different methods of pathological investigations with unusual sites

Types of Pathological investigation	Specimen	Total
Fluid cytology	Ascitic-1 Pleural – 03 Scrotal fluid -01	05
FNAC	Breast lump- 3 Inguinal lymph node-2 Thyroid-2 Subcutaneous nodule in forearm -1	08
Biopsy	Inguinal lymph node – 2 Breast lump- 1	03
Total		16

Discussion

Microfilaria is a major public health problem in tropical countries and it is epidemic in many areas of states of India like Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh, Orissa, Kerala, and Gujarat including Chhattisgarh. It has many species of nematodes like *Wuchereria bancrofti*, *Brugia malayi*, *B. timori*, *Loa-loa*, *Onchocerca volvulus*, *Mansonella perstans*, *M. ozzardi*. [6] *Wuchereria bancrofti* (90%) and *Brugia malayi* (10%) are the most common species responsible for microfilaria in India. [1,7,8,] Most frequently, this disease involves mainly lymphatic system of lower limbs, retroperitoneal tissue, spermatic cord, epididymis and mammary gland. [4,9] It can also identify in pleural, pericardial, ascitic fluid, ovarian cyst fluid, breast lump, aspirates like bone marrow, thyroid and also in parotid and gall bladder. [8,10] Many authors have reported microfilariae in breast lumps in FNAC smears which was also found in our study. [1,8,10] Microfilaria parasite demonstrated in cytological smears from many unusual sites is an incidental finding. [2,11] Finding of microfilaria in subcutaneous forearm nodule is rare [12,13] where as we reported one case in subcutaneous nodule of forearm. Our study reveals microfilaria infestation in a wide range of pathological samples, highlighting their ability to adapt and thrive in diverse environments. This challenges our current understanding of microfilaria habitat and emphasizes the need for an expanded diagnostic approach, including: Multidisciplinary collaboration, improved detection methods, broader sampling strategies.

Conclusion

In India, many states are endemic for filarial infection. FNAC and fluid cytology is a rapid, simple procedure and a diagnostic tool for the diagnosis of microfilaria. Therefore, it is necessary to examine carefully FNAC, body fluids and histopathological sections from different sites of unsuspected swelling for microfilaria. Microfilaria should always be considered as one of differential diagnosis. Smears and tissue sections should be screened carefully which will be helpful to detect

the incidental presence of microfilaria, even in asymptomatic patients and chance of associated finding with other pathologies.

This research paper presents a ground-breaking discovery, unveiling the unprecedented presence of microfilariae in various pathological samples. Our findings have significant implications for the diagnosis, treatment, and management of filarial diseases, underscoring the importance of considering microfilaria infestation in diverse clinical contexts. Future studies should investigate the mechanisms of microfilaria migration and the clinical consequences of their presence in unconventional sites.

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